

Best practices for Open Science (OS) & Intellectual Property (IP)

Welcome to this survey on best practices for Open Science and Intellectual Property. This survey is part of the Horizon Europe Unpacking the possibilities of Intellectual Properties for Open Science (IP4OS) project, which explores how intellectual property can support open science rather than hinder it. The aim is to develop the Synergy Framework, a practical guide for balancing protection of intellectual assets with open research practices.

Throughout this survey, the acronyms OS and IP are used frequently, referring to Open Science and Intellectual Property respectively:

OS refers to the full range of practices under Open Science. We take a broad view that includes all aspects of openness in research, from data sharing and open access to collaboration and transparency in methods.

IP covers all aspects of intellectual property valorisation in the context of research and innovation—from its identification and management to its use in partnerships, collaborations, licensing, and commercialisation.

Your insights matter. The information you share will directly inform the Synergy Framework, helping ensure it reflects practical realities across disciplines, sectors, and institutions. By taking part, you're contributing to a more coherent and workable approach to OS and IP in the European research landscape.

Please note: This survey will close on 25 May 2025 at 23:59 (CEST). Kindly ensure you complete and submit your responses before this date.

Data Security and ConfidentialityYour responses will be anonymised and handled in compliance with the GDPR. All data will be stored securely, processed solely for research and policy purposes, and will not be shared in a way that could identify individual respondents. If you would like more information on how your responses will be secured and processed or if you have any other concerns, please contact us at gustav.nilsonne@ki.se or gautam.sharma@ki.se.
Informed ConsentBy proceeding, you confirm that you understand the purpose of this survey and consent to your responses being used for research and policy development. Your participation is voluntary, and you may exit the survey at any time. Thank you for your time and valuable input!

Section 1: Background

What is your primary professional role? (Select all that apply.)

- Researcher
- Administrator from a Higher Education Institution (HEI)
- Public/Private Research Performing Organization (RPO) Representative
- Scholarly Communications Librarian
- Other Librarian
- Publisher (Scholarly / Open Access)
- Industry Partner
- Policymaker
- Research Manager
- Ethics Committee Member
- Research Funding Professional
- Knowledge/Technology Transfer Officer (TTO) / University IP Commercialisation Representative
- Legal Expert (IPR / Patent Attorney / IP Consultant / Advisor)
- Patent Office Representative
- Digital Repository Specialist
- Science Communicator / Journalist
- Citizen Science Representative
- Data Protection Officer
- Other (please specify)

If you selected "Other," please specify your role:

Which sector do you primarily work in? (Select all that apply.)

- Academia (e.g., universities, research institutions)
- Industry (e.g., corporate R&D, biotech, pharma)
- Innovation Support (e.g., knowledge technology transfer offices, incubators, accelerators, patent and IP advisory services, EEN, etc.)
- Research support staff (e.g., data stewards, research coordinators, etc.)
- Government / Policy (e.g., regulatory bodies, government agencies)
- Non-Profit / NGO (e.g., advocacy groups, foundations)
- Publishing (e.g., academic, commercial publishing)
- Research Funding Body (e.g., grant agencies, foundations, research councils)
- Other (please specify)

If you selected "Other," please specify the sector

What is the name of your primary institution or organisation? (Please provide the full name of the institution you are affiliated with.)

In which country is your institution or organisation based? (If your organisation operates in multiple countries, select the one most relevant to your work.)

How would you rate your expertise in Open Science and Intellectual Property?

	Not familiar	Slightly familiar	Moderately familiar	Very familiar	Expert
Open Science (OS)	<input type="radio"/>				
Intellectual Property (IP)	<input type="radio"/>				
Concerted OS and IP (the use of OS and IP together in a supportive manner)	<input type="radio"/>				

Have you directly worked on policies or agreements involving both or either Open Science and Intellectual Property? Yes No

What type(s) of intellectual property rights do you deal with most? (Select all that apply.)

- Patents
- Copyrights
- Trademarks
- Industrial Designs and Aesthetic Innovations
- Geographical Indications
- Trade Secrets & Know-How
- Plant Variety Rights
- None of the above
- Others (please specify)

If you selected "Others," please specify: _____

Section 2: Perceptions of Open Science & IP

How do you perceive the relationship between Open Science (OS) and Intellectual Property (IP)? Rate each statement on a scale from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral / Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
OS and IP are fundamentally contradictory.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
OS and IP can be synergistic with the right policies.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
OS and IP work well together in my field.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
IP hinders OS more than it enables it.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
OS challenges traditional IP models but can be integrated.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
IP can support Open Science or vice-versa.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

What do you see as the biggest obstacles in harmonising Open Science (OS) and Intellectual Property (IP)? (Rate each on a scale of 1-5: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral / Neither Agree nor Disagree, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree.)

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral / Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Legal uncertainties	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Institutional resistance	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Licensing complexities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Different missions/interests of universities, research performing organisations, and businesses	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lack of awareness & understanding	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Risk of publishing compromising patentability due to prior disclosure	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Do you see any other obstacles in harmonising Open Science and Intellectual Property?

What factors do you think help researchers apply the best Intellectual Property (IP) tools and Open Science (OS) practices? (Select all that apply.)

- Understanding what level of reuse of research outputs should be targeted (e.g., no reuse, restricted/exclusive reuse, free or open reuse)
- Knowing when in the research and cooperation lifecycle IP should be applied
- Awareness of what IP measures are in place
- Other (please specify)

If you have selected "Other," please specify:

Section 3: Real-World Challenges & Solutions

Have you personally experienced a situation where Open Science and Intellectual Property were in conflict?

- Yes
- No

If yes, can you describe the situation(s) where Open Science and Intellectual Property were at odds, and how was this conflict resolved (or was it not resolved)?

(Please describe any relevant experience. What was the situation about, and who were the key stakeholders? How did it affect research or innovation? What steps were taken to address it? Did legal frameworks, policies, or agreements play a role? Were any compromises needed? What lessons did you or your organisation take from it?)

What successful models have you seen for balancing Open Science and Intellectual Property? (Select all that apply.)

- Open licensing models (e.g., Creative Commons)
- Institutional policies supporting OS while protecting IP
- Collaborative IP sharing agreements (e.g., patent pools, FRAND models)
- Other (please specify)

If "Other," please specify:

Can you share a real case where Intellectual Property (IP) were used to support Open Science (OS), or OS practices were used to support IP?

- Yes
- No

If you answered yes, could you describe the situation? What methods were used to find a balance? Who were the key players involved? What were the positive outcomes?

You may omit names or personal identifiers if you prefer.

Have you observed any other best practice examples that have worked well for OS-IP integration? (We welcome examples from any sector. Have you encountered a specific policy, law, or institutional strategy that effectively balances OS and IP? How did it function, and what were the key takeaways?)

Rank the most important policy interventions to improve the Open Science (OS) - Intellectual Property (IP) balance.
(Rate each on a scale of 1-5: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral / Neither Agree nor Disagree, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree.)

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral / Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Clarifying the compatibility between OS practices and research commercialization.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Mandate Open Access and Open Data for publicly funded research.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Provide clear licensing frameworks for OS-friendly IP management.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Offer academic incentives for collaborative innovation and OS adoption.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Strengthen researcher (& industry) training on OS-IP policies and best practices.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Promote standardisation and compliance mechanisms for OS-IP interoperability.

Section 4: Future Engagement & Follow-Up

Would you be open to a follow-up discussion or interview?

 Yes No

Would you be interested in receiving the final report on a concerted IP-OS approach based on this survey?

 Yes No

If you answered yes, please provide your email ID so we can follow up with you.
